

A new approach for the sensitive detection of thiols in food by affinity solid phase extraction and GC-MS

Stephan Neumann^{1,2}, Egon Gross², Stephanie Korte², Birgit Kohlenberg², Melanie Esselen¹, Hans-Ulrich Humpf¹ and JOHANNES KIEFL²

¹ Institute of Food Chemistry, University of Muenster, Corrensstrasse 45, 48149 Muenster, Germany;

² Symrise AG, Muehlenfeldstrasse 1, 37603 Holzminden, Germany; johannes.kiefl@symrise.com

Abstract

Sulphur containing volatile molecules belong to the most aroma active components in food with reported concentrations below 1 µg/L. Various extraction methods have been developed in the past to enrich thiols and improve detectability [1-4]. Here, we describe the development of a new extraction protocol using 2-thiopyridyl disulphide activated agarose gel (known as thiopropyl-sepharose 6B, TPS) commonly used for protein analysis [5]. Primary, secondary and tertiary thiols namely 1-hexanethiol, 2-furfurylthiol, 2-phenylethanethiol, pentane-2-thiol, 3-mercaptohexyl acetate, 2-methyltetrahydrofuran-3-thiol, 4-methoxy-2-methyl-2-butanethiol, 4-mercapto-4-methyl-2-pentanone, 1-p-menthene-8-thiol and p-mentha-8-thiol-3-one were used to study the binding affinity of the stationary phase. The optimization of the overall extraction parameters was performed by a design of experiment (DOE) approach. A selective enrichment and concentration was achieved by factor up to 70 for primary thiols on TPS and by an additional factor up to 5000 for stir bar sorptive extraction (SBSE) of the ethanolic extract obtained after elution of bound thiols with tris(2-carboxyethyl)phosphine. Limit of detection levels less than 1 µg/L could be achieved by combining TPS based extraction with SBSE-gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS).

Keywords: thiols, enrichment, thiopropyl-sepharose, aroma, affinity solid phase extraction

Introduction

Extraction and derivatization of thiols with reagents such as 4-vinylpyridine [1], ebselen [2] and disulphide reagents such as 6,6'-dithiodinicotinic acid [3] and 4,4'-dithiodipyridine [4] are used to sensitively analyse known thiols with liquid chromatography mass spectrometry. In the contrary, fewer methodologies for affinity based solid phase extraction such as mercuric benzoate linked agarose gel are reported [6]. An alternative protocol was developed for the mercuric benzoate based method for occupational safety reasons using 2-thiopyridyl-disulphide activated agarose gel by a covalent chromatography based on thiol-disulphide exchange reaction [5] for enrichment of free thiols. The latter is used for protein analysis but was so far not adopted for extraction of aroma-active thiols in food.

Experimental

The following reference compounds were obtained in the highest available grade of purity: 2-pentanethiol, 1-p-menthene-8-thiol, 2-methyltetrahydrofuran-3-thiol, 2-furfurylthiol, 4-mercapto-4-methyl-2-pentanone, p-mentha-8-thiol-3-one (ThermoFischer Scientific, Karlsruhe, Germany); 4-methoxy-2-methyl-2-butanethiol, 2-phenylethanethiol, 3-mercaptohexyl acetate, 1-hexanethiol (Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany). A 1000 mg/kg stock solution of the references in ethanol was freshly prepared and further diluted with deionized water (Arium mini, Sartorius, Germany) to 100 mg/kg (model stock solution) prior use. Further, a coupling buffer was prepared by solubilizing 18.61 mg ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid disodium salt dehydrate (EDTA-Na₂ H₂O) (1 mmol/L) and 1.46 g sodium chloride (NaCl) (0.5 mol/L) in 50 mL phosphate buffer (67 mmol/L, pH 7.5). To release thiols bound on TPS resin (thiopropyl-sepharose 6B, Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany), the disulphide bridge was reduced with a solution of tris(2 carboxyethyl)phosphine hydrochloride (TCEP HCl) (100 mmol/kg). Therefore, 710 mg of TCEP HCl and 9.3 mg EDTA-Na₂ H₂O were sonicated in 12.5 g phosphate buffer (67 mmol/L, pH 7.5) followed by addition of sodium hydroxide solution (1 mol/L) for pH readjustment (pH = 7.5) and finally 12.5 g ethanol. It is important to keep the order of dissolution to pre-dissolve TCEP HCl in water.

Extraction protocol

Enrichment of free thiols was performed by using a thiol-affinity and cross-linked TPS resin with reactive 2-thiopyridyl disulphide groups linked to hydroxypropanol via ether bonds (Figure 1). Free thiols are bound and released by thiol-disulphide exchange reaction referred to as covalent chromatography. The freeze-dried resin was rehydrated by weighing 150 mg TPS resin in a 2 mL safe-lock tube, adding 1.5 mL deionized water and incubating it at room temperature for 15 min. Subsequently, sedimented resin was homogenized gently by using a 1000 µL pipette and left at room temperature for additional 15 min.

The settled resin was transferred to a 2 mL empty SPE-cartridge with an integrated frit and was connected to a SPE-Baker-Box by a Lure-lock valve. Excessive water was removed under reduced pressure. The gel was gently washed with 9 mL deionized water followed by gently washing with 6 mL of coupling buffer. In the next step an aliquot of 1000 μ L of the free thiol containing model solution (120 mL) was added to the prewashed resin and was then quantitatively transferred to a 200 mL Erlenmeyer flask. This suspension was shaken on an IKA shaker (KS 130 basic, IKA Works, Inc., Wilmington, USA) for 6 hours at 400 rpm and room temperature. After shaking, the suspension was transferred back to the previous used SPE-cartridge, left to settle down and washed by adding 40 mL EtOH followed by 40 mL EtOH/H₂O (1+1, w/w).

After washing, the valve was closed and 1 g of the prepared TCEP solution (100 mmol/kg) was added followed by gentle homogenization and incubation at room temperature for 20 min. Finally, the solution was eluted in a 2 mL auto sampler vial followed by addition of 100 μ L hydrochloric acid (1 mol/L) to prevent possible side reactions like thiol disulphide exchange reactions and dimerization.

To achieve a further enrichment of thiols, the stir bar sorptive extraction (SBSE) was used. Therefore, 200 mg of eluate and 800 mg water were combined in a 2 mL auto sampler vial, the stir bar (PDMS Twister with 1 mm layer thickness and 10 mm length, Gerstel, Muelheim, Germany) was added, the vial sealed with a cap and stirred on a magnetic stirrer for 1 hour at 600 rpm and room temperature. The stir bar was removed after this extraction and gently rinsed with few millilitres of deionized water and carefully dried with clean paper towels and transferred to a thermal desorption unit for measurement (TDU, Gerstel, Muelheim, Germany).

GC-MS/FID analysis

Sample volatiles were transferred to the GC by desorbing the Twister at 280 °C for 10 min in the Gerstel thermal desorption unit, then the analytes were cryo-focussed at -30 °C in the cooled injection system inlet containing a Tenax filled glass liner and then desorbed at 280 °C for 10 min onto the GC column, where the analytes were separated on an Agilent Technologies DB-1ms (60 m x 0.32 mm, 0.25 μ m, Agilent, Waldbronn, Germany) placed in an Agilent 7890A gas chromatograph (Waldbronn, Germany) using helium as the carrier gas. A constant flow of 2 mL/min was applied. The GC temperature was programmed starting at 40 °C, held for 2 min, then raised at 4 °C/min to 300 °C, and held for 75 min. Retention indices were calculated by chromatography of a homologous series of n-alkanes from C6 to C30. The effluent was split and transferred to the FID set at 300 °C and MS set in scan mode (EI ionization 70 eV, m/z 33 – 450, 3.4 scans/sec). The yield of recovered primary, secondary and tertiary thiols was determined by extracting model solution with 100 mg/kg of each thiol with TPS and dividing the analysed concentration (using external calibration) by expected 100 mg/kg. External calibration with internal standard 1-hexanethiol and GC-FID was used for quantitation and assessment of validation parameters. Recovery rate was determined by division of quantitated amount and spiked amount of thiol times 100. Data were acquired by Agilent MSD ChemStation version E.02.02.

Design of experiments (DOE)

A sequential approach using DOE principles was set up to study sample preparation parameters on thiol recovery rates. After preliminary trials, a rotatable Central Composite Design (CCD) with three continuous factors and six centre points was designed. The parameters and their maximum border values were binding time (29.6 – 120 min), sample volume (19.5 – 500 ml) and desorption time (9.6 – 90.4 min). The composition of the sample itself was kept constant comprising a predefined mixture of reference thiols.

In a second generally comparable CCD-attempt, the objective was to investigate the influence of the factors (i) thiol concentration (5 – 50 μ g/kg), (ii) amount of TPS (mg) and (iii) pH-value (3 – 9) on recovery rates at 6-hour constant exposure time.

The results from both designs were modelled using the standard least square approach while fitting and optimizing all models simultaneously to enable a simultaneous interpretation of the independent factors obeying the heredity. This more general modelling approach was chosen in order to get an overall describing model for all occurring effects. Due to the high skewness of the analytical results, a log₁₀-transformation was necessary to overcome the non-normal distribution prior to the modelling procedure.

Results and discussion

The goal of this study was to develop an alternative sample preparation protocol to mercury based thiol extraction. This protocol uses covalent chromatography based on thiol-disulphide exchange reaction [5] for enrichment of free thiols in liquid food samples on the TPS solid phase. Free thiols were bound on this commercially available activated agarose resin with 2-thiopyridyldisulphide as the active group (Figure 1) and with a binding capacity of 18 to 31 μ mol/ml of resin.

Figure 1: Mechanism of covalent binding of free thiol (R_1 -SH) with 2-thiopyridyldisulphide activated agarose.

In a first step, a free nucleophile thiolate attacks the sulphur atom next to the 2-thiopyridine leaving group to perform a new disulphide bond under release of 2-thiopyridone. 2-Thiopyridone exists in a thiol-thione tautomeric form and reacts under oxidative autocatalysis to 2,2'-dithiodipyridine [7]. The matrix bound thiols are then released by reduction with tris(2-carboxyethyl)phosphine (TCEP).

The principle of binding free thiols to disulphide reactants such as 6,6'-dithiodinicotinic acid [3] and 4,4'-dithiodipyridine [4] is well known and was early adapted for aroma analysis. However, these reactants have been developed to measure the degree of reaction by photometry or liquid chromatography of derivatized thiols. The analysis of derivatization products aims at increasing sensitivity by reacting analytes with highly detector responsive groups, which is useful for detection and quantitation of known thiols. However, derivatized thiols cannot be sniffed by GC-Olfactometry, the lack of mass spectrometric information especially EI-MS fragmentation pattern limits the identification and the derivatization process does not include a concentration step. In contrast, thiols derivatized with agarose bound 2-thiopyridyldisulphide can be released after concentration and analysed by GC-MS/O.

Initial optimisation trials with TPS revealed a binding capacity of 2.5 μmol per 35 mg resin, tested with model solutions of 2-furfurylthiol at different concentrations. Next, the binding of the thiols in a continuous flow mode was tested by transferring the resin to the empty SPE-cartridge and slowly passing 250 mL of model solution under reduced pressure for 82 min. The yield of recovered thiols showed that the contact time was too short to quantitatively bind free thiols (data not shown). Therefore, the washed resin was transferred from the SPE-cartridge to a flask and reacted under static condition. Dithiothreitol and TCEP were tested as reducing agent and TCEP was found to give higher yields (data not shown). Finally, liquid injection (GC-MS/FID), dynamic headspace (DHS)-GC-MS/FID and SBSE-GC-MS/FID were tested to analyse the eluate and SBSE-GC-MS/FID technique with a polydimethyl siloxane (PDMS) coated Twister (Gerstel) was chosen.

The extraction of free thiols in liquid samples by using TPS resin causes a structure-dependent enrichment. A design of experiment (DOE) approach was conducted to systematically study the effect of pH value, concentration of educts, exposure time and release with TCEP on the yield of recovered primary, secondary and tertiary thiols in model solution. The exposure time was set to 6 hours yielding the best overall thiol recovery ($p < 0.001$). The DOE data further show that the pH-value affects the binding of primary, secondary and tertiary thiols alike ($p < 0.001$). The greater the pH value the higher the reactivity of free thiols with an observed optimum of pH 7.5. Furthermore, the amount of TPS and thiol concentration was identified as significantly impacting the recovery of primary and secondary thiols ($p < 0.007$ and $p < 0.007$) although no saturation of active sides could take place. Primary thiols like 2-phenylethanthiol (75% yield, enrichment factor of 70) and also secondary thiols like 3-mercaptohexyl acetate (in average 80% yield, enrichment factor 25) achieve a higher recovery than tertiary thiols like *p*-mentha-8-thiol-3-one (in average 30% yield, enrichment factor 10).

This extraction leads to a selective depletion of non-sulphurous flavour compounds facilitating mass spectrometric identification of unknown thiols in complex matrices. For example, a Scheurebe white wine from Franconia has been spiked with sulphur compounds (no. 1-8) at 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ and was measured before enrichment (A) and after thiol enrichment (B) (Figure 2).

This new methodology was validated by external calibration with 1-hexanethiol internal standard (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, Table 1) in white wine conducting TPS based extraction. Recovery rates were calculated as average of measurements at concentration levels of 0.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ and 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$.

Figure 2: Comparison of two SBSE-GC-MS-chromatograms before enrichment (A) and after thiol enrichment (B) of a Scheurebe white wine from Franconia spiked with thiol model solution at 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ (no. 1-8).

Table 1: Summary of validation results for spiked Franconin white wine.

no	compound	calibration curve			sensitivity				
		R ²	slope	intercept	linearity [$\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$]	LOD [$\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$]	LOQ [$\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$]	recovery [%]	RSD [%]
1	pentane-2-thiol	0.9992	0.0473	-0.03	52 - 520	33.2	52.0	110.0	5.3
2	2-furfurylthiol	0.9989	0.2228	0.06	58 - 1154	15.3	57.7	132.7	1.7
3	4-methoxy-2-methylbutane-2-thiol	0.9958	0.6592	0.23	4.9 - 491	0.50	4.93	62.1	11.7
4	4-mercapto-4-methylpentane-2-one	0.9946	0.3577	0.13	5.0 - 496	0.98	4.98	144.5	11.1
5	2-phenylethanethiol	0.9999	1.1025	-0.05	5.3 - 524	5.10	5.26	93.8	0.6
6	3-mercaptohexyl acetate	0.9985	0.8291	0.22	5.5 - 547	2.52	5.49	115.7	1.5
7	1- <i>p</i> -menthene-8-thiol	0.9992	0.6874	-0.12	5.3 - 529	4.06	5.31	157.5	2.3
8	<i>p</i> -mentha-8-thiol-3-one ¹	0.9958	0.6687	0.20	6.6 - 656	0.66	6.59	47.9	9.9

¹ *trans* and *cis* form.

TPS based extraction combined with SBSE-GC-MS/FID achieved low LOD values like 0.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ for 4-methoxy-2-methylbutane-2-thiol, mostly quantitative recovery and relative standard deviation of mostly < 10%.

References

- Katritzky, A. R.; Takahashi, I.; Marson, C. M., 2-(4-Pyridyl)ethyl as a protecting group for sulfur functionality, *Org Chem.* 1986;51(25):4914-4920.
- Vichi, S.; Cortés-Francisco, N.; Romero, A.; Caixach, J., Determination of volatile thiols in virgin olive oil by derivatisation and LC-HRMS, and relation with sensory attributes *Food Chem.* 2014;149:313-318.
- Nishiyama, J.; Kuninori, T., Assay of biological thiols by a combination of high-performance liquid chromatography and postcolumn reaction with 6, 6'-dithiodinicotinic acid, *Anal Biochem.* 1984;138(1):95-98.
- Capone, D. L.; Ristic, R.; Pardon, K. H.; Jeffery, D. W., Simple quantitative determination of potent thiols at ultratrace levels in wine by derivatization and high-performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS/MS) analysis, *Anal Chem.* 2015;87(2):1226-1231.
- Brocklehurst, K.; Carlsson, J.; Kierstan, M. P. J.; Crook, E. M., In *Methods in Enzymology*, Kaplan, N. P.; Colowick, N. P.; Jakoby, W. B.; Wilchek, M., Covalent chromatography by thiol-disulfide interchange, Eds. Academic Press: 1974; Vol. 34, pp 531-544.
- Full, G.; Schreier, P., A valuable method for the aroma analysis of thiols at trace levels, *Lebensmittelchemie* 1994;48:1-4.
- Stoyanov, S.; Petkov, I.; Antonov, L.; Stoyanova, T.; Karagiannidis, P.; Aslanidis, P., Thione-thiol tautomerism and stability of 2- and 4-mercaptopyridines and 2-mercaptopyrimidines, *Can J Chem.* 1990;68(9):1482-1489.